

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN SCHOOLS FOR THE BVI IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article investigates the usage of modern technologies for teaching English to blind and visually impaired students. Modern technologies are an important aid to English teachers when they are used effectively.

Keywords: blind and visually impaired (BVI), modern classroom technologies, tactile learning, Braille, audio lessons, Grammar Cube.

Every child tries to imagine and understand the world he lives in from the early days. Children with visual disabilities try to adapt to life where the majority of people see and think of the world in a different way. They build relationship with people from an early ages and struggle with communication of the outer world. The way they perceive the world and classroom atmosphere is quite different from those without any impairment. As a result, they might experience challenges while developing language skills and require additional assistance. Thus, the usage of the latest technologies in the English classroom gives more effect in developing BVI listening and speaking skills. The purpose of this paper is to bring to light some issues that schools for BVI are experiencing and present some of the modern technologies that could be used effectively in teaching EFL to blind and visually impaired learners.

Like other subjects, English is also taught in the schools of Uzbekistan, and the role of modern classroom technologies for blind and visually impaired students is believed to be significantly effective. There are specialized schools for students with disabilities in every region of the country. According to the press service of public education, the total number of schools in the country for children with visual impairments and blind children is 15. The total number of students studying in these schools² is 3,370. In these types of schools, only two foreign languages (English and German) are being taught to all grades (1-11) (Press Service, Ministry of Public School of Uzbekistan). Unfortunately, teachers and students still face a number of challenges in teaching and learning English as a second language in such schools. The most significant issue is that these foreign language textbooks are not in Braille format. Agesa and Arslantas (2017) argue that visually impaired students pose difficulties in learning a foreign language since human vision serves as a major

stimulus for learning a language. Another problem stems from the use of public-school textbooks instead of Braille textbooks. The theme of the lesson is learnt quickly or slowly, depending on the differences in vision ability of the student. While language learners with slightly lower visual acuity learn the subject more effectively via public school textbooks, blind learners are completely deprived of this opportunity. The impairment only becomes a disability when the ambient society creates environments with barriers (DePoy & Gilson, 2011). People who are blind and visually impaired are capable to learn any subject as other healthy people. The conditions for learning English in schools for healthy children should also be created for schools with BVI students. Despite their disability, these students have the same rights as other unimpaired students. In general, what modern technologies are most effective in teaching visually impaired students?

Utilization of modern assistive technologies to teach English to BVI students

Teaching BVI students is completely different from teaching unimpaired students. Indeed, unimpaired students can obtain knowledge by using any of the learning styles. However, students with visual impairment are expected to learn better by using their sense of touch and hearing ability. They learn by listening and touching (Willoughby, 1985). The teacher who teaches EFL to BVI students should be very accurate with his voice since, as it was mentioned above, this type of learners are only able to receive the information without seeing it. The teacher should have all the needed tools in hand while having his English lessons. General technology such computers, commercially available toys, do-it-yourself tools and Braille writers can be a great assistance for the teacher who is experienced in utilizing them. However, using the tools that mentioned above requires much funds and not many schools can afford it. Therefore, the followings are considered to be more empirical for schools for visually impaired in Uzbekistan: audio courses/lessons, screen readers, voice programs and grammar cubes.

English teaching audio courses

Many audio lessons and listening exercises are part of English learning, and the learning procedure goes in conjunction with pictures or videos. However, in addition to lessons that use visual aids, there are also courses in a full audio format that can be partially used as a guide for teaching English to BVI learners. With the assistance of such courses, teachers of schools for blind and impaired learners can improve the level of knowledge of their students from the elementary to the intermediate level. A BVI student can explore a variety of everyday English topics such as Shopping, Weather, Directions or other conversations in and out of class. However, these audio courses have disadvantages. They can't help to enrich students' vocabulary. Consequently, BVI students will have difficulties in working independently, and additional aids can be helpful (English vocabulary in Braille).

Screen readers and voice programs

It is known that computer science classes are held in schools for BVI students. In these classes, students learn to work on a computer. Their computer skills also can help them to learn English. All they need is a Braille keyboard and a screen reader software. The teacher conducts the English lesson on a computer. The screen provides text, grammar exercises, tests, and problem-solving assignments, depending on the students' level of English proficiency.

Grammar cubes

Grammar cubes can be used to teach grammar, in particular, Simple tenses, imperatives, and modals in an intuitive kinesthetic way (Stipichev P.A., 2015). Though this tool has limited words for usage, it is simple to use and can be used in classroom (too many ‘use’ in one sentence. Consider paraphrasing, i.e. Though this tool provides a limited number of words, it is easy to use in a classroom). The tool helps students improve their vocabulary, word building and reading.

Android apps

There are dozens of android applications that can be used to acquire a knowledge of English language by visually impaired users. Depending on students' English level some of the English learning android apps can be skillfully used by the teacher in or out of the classroom. For instance, teacher asks his students to do a home assignment (a short text, poem) using “A voice brief” app which reads content aloud. One more android app is “Audible”. BVI students can use audible as a good book reader tool to improve his listening skills.

Braille textbooks

Moreover, every specialized school for students with disabilities has a library where the Ministry of public education and some charity organizations deliver-books and textbooks for the school students. Every library should have special books (Braille) for blind and visually impaired visitors. The opportunity to print new generation books in 3D printers should also be given to the schools for BVI students in Uzbekistan. In addition, each publication should have its audio as visually impaired and sightless students develop their listening skills, they would accept this facility with great pleasure. All in all, audios for books in libraries should be organized by the ministry or school administration.

While teaching, English teachers of BVI students should take into consideration that students who sit in front of them would like to learn a foreign language similar to unimpaired students. Time issues are to be taken into account when teaching BVI classrooms. Every English teacher should realize the significance of modern technology used in the classroom. Freire FMP and Prado MEBB (1998) argue that the success of using information technology for educational purposes depends on a collaborative effort between the school and the teachers, requiring planning that

considers the needs and conditions of the school so that issues such as equipment maintenance and material supplies do not become an obstacle.

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